

COMMON NUTRITIONAL PROBLEMS AMONG CHILDREN IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF OYO STATE

Omosebi, M.O.¹, Oluokun, M.A.², Emiola L.M.³ and Shehu, R.A.³

¹Department of Food Science and Technology, Wesley University of Science and Technology, P.O. Box 507, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria, ² College Clinic, Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Oyo State, Nigeria, ³Department of Human Kinetics & Health Education, University Of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The study examined the common nutritional problems among children in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo State. A descriptive research design was used, while the study population consisted of nurses and nursing mothers. These people represented the group of respondents used in the study. In all, one hundred and fifty respondents in the area of study were randomly selected. The variables tested in the area of study include common nutritional problems like kwashiorkor, marasmus, anaemia and ricket among many others. Data was collected through the use of a self-designed questionnaire, duly validated and tested for reliability. The two results of test retest methods were later compared and correlation co-efficient of 0.65r was obtained, the level of correlation is considered acceptable for the study. The data was processed using simple percentage, mean score and chi-square at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The result revealed that children in Oyo East Local Government do not significantly suffer from the most common nutritional deficiencies diseases such as kwashiorkor, marasmus, anaemia and ricket. Based on the findings, It was recommended among others that adequate balanced diet should be given to children, through advocacy and antenatal education. Also, the health workers should encourage and educate nursing mothers on the importance of proper de-worming of children from time to time to prevent worm infestation which may lead to nutritional anaemia and to avoid cultural taboos that prevent children and nursing mothers from eating proteinous food like meat and snail among many others.

KEYWORDS: Balanced diet, Energy- giving foods, Food, Kwashiorkor, Malnutrition, Marasmus, Proteinous food

INTRODUCTION

According to Samuel *et al.* (1985), food is a substance which yields materials, produces energy and growth, repairs body tissues, regulates body functions, and which should not be harmful to the body. The commonest class of food that is available in Nigeria is carbohydrate. Proper diet should be eaten by everybody especially children because this is one of the basic needs for sound health. There are different types of culture and each has different types of food that are common to them. The choice of staple food may be influenced by the geographical location of the area, economic condition, belief systems as well as the availability of the food in a particular locality (Mclaren, 1976, Payne and Hahn, 1998).

The types of food eaten vary from one society to the other. The food eaten by one society may not be eaten in another society due to religion, culture, taboo and other related factors. According to Mohammed and Fritz (1996), avoidance of specific types of food is a widespread phenomenon mostly common to food of animal origin. Religion and other beliefs often call for this avoidance, but other cultural factors can also be involved. Some foods are regarded as being of low prestige for instance; most people avoid consuming the meat of animals that died of natural causes, especially if they died of disease. This natural trait is strengthened by injunctions of the major religions. However belief can differ sharply. Important examples of food commonly avoided are pork among Jews, Muslims and Ethiopian Christians; beef among Hindus, some Buddhists and Jains; dog meat among the Christians and Muslims; fish in Mongolia and other parts of central Asia; milk and milk products in Polynesia and parts of China. (Mohammed and Fritz, 1996).

Viedma (1988) stated that nutritional balance is something that is built up day by day right from the time when the embryo starts to form in the mother's womb. Indeed, it is at this point that the problem of growth and development begins. A great number of new born babies of the developing countries die or fail to thrive because of vicious spiral or recurrent infections and chronic under nutrition from mothers who become pregnant with a poor nutritional status and remain improperly nourished throughout pregnancy and lactation.

In the case of nursing mothers, they feed their new born babies with breast milk, boiled water and herbs. After four or five months of delivery, children are fed with pap, which according to these mothers could give the children energy. When the children are old enough to eat solid food, they are then fed with carbohydrate food items such as "*amala*", "*eba*", yam, pounded yam and "*fufu*" (Mohammed & Fritz, 1996).

Barbara and Huda, (1991) recommended that preventive health measure such as proper nutrition should be instituted as early as possible, preferably in childhood or early adulthood. In fact, the scientific evidence which links dietary practices with the preventive and treatment of major chronic diseases is increasingly abundant. There are particularly convincing data on the role of diet (low fat, particularly animal fats and low cholesterol) in the heart disease prevention. There are also data suggesting that eating foods with a higher fiber and low fat content and possibly other nutrients helps prevent certain forms of cancer (especially cancers of the large bowel and breast). Excessive calorie intake and the excess body fat that goes with it is also associated with the development of diabetes in adults. Certain genetic determinants will predispose an individual to specific chronic diseases. Nevertheless, preventive dietary practices offer consumers a pivotal role to play in maintaining their own health.

The importance of classes of food to the body cannot be over-emphasized. For instance, low intake of protein can lead to health problems in the child (Bengoa, 1974). Malnutrition in the developing countries often leads to protein deficiency-related diseases which rarely occur in countries that have abundant supply of protein-given foods (Payne and Hahn, 1998).

In Latin American cities, malnutrition was said to be directly responsible for more than 50% of the death of children under five years of age (Suskind, 1997). It can thus be strongly asserted that food is the basis of sound health. During metabolism, digested foods are absorbed and finally distributed to the body system where they are used. If anything goes wrong with this process, nutritional disorder then sets in. Nutrition becomes disordered as a result of any deviation from the normal digestive process. Thus, evidences have shown that malnutrition is improper feeding; either over or under-feeding, or poor or wrong feeding, a situation which makes a particular child receive insufficient food nutrients in the body. Such a child victim, mostly, between 0-10 years look thin, poorly postured with protruding stomach, grey hairs and sunken eyes. Such a child is said to be suffering from nutritional deficiency which indicates that the child is not well fed with the correct balanced diet (Mclaren, 1976).

Malnutrition is however, not the only problem facing children but it is the most easily demonstrated and measured. It is the intent of this study to elicit valuable and gainful pieces of information about the nutritional status of children in Oyo East local government area. The data may also reflect nutritional deficiencies in other areas within the state. Oyo East local government area being the research setting is located in the eastern part of Oyo town in Oyo state .It is about 40kilometers away from Ibadan, the state capital of Oyo state, Nigeria. The people are mainly Yorubas and a few are from other tribes. They are mostly farmers; they cultivate main crops like cassava, maize, yam, beans and cocoyam. Many inhabitants are skilled carvers, iron welders, mechanics, carpenters, teachers, etc. The people speak Yoruba and English and are mainly Muslims and Christians.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design.

The purpose of this work was to determine the prevailing nutritional deficiencies among children in Oyo town of Oyo East local government area of Oyo state. To this end, a descriptive design was used, and survey method was used to determine the prevalence of the problem(s). Gay (1987) defined descriptive research as the collection of data in order to test hypotheses (if any), or answer research questions concerning the current status of the subject of the study.

Population

The total population of this study comprised of nursing mothers and nurses that live and work in hospitals located in Oyo East local government authority of Oyo state. The census of nursing mothers of the area was taken through the use of hospital registers of nursing mothers that attended post-natal clinic in the following health institutions in Oyo East local government namely: State Hospital, Oyo (150), Ajagba Maternity Centre (90), Oba Adeyemi Maternity Centre, Oyo (90), Local Government Child Welfare Centre, Oyo (60), Oke-Apo Maternity Centre (60)

This shows that a total population of 450 nursing mothers attends clinics in Oyo town in recent times. The census of the nurses working in the above hospitals was also taken and a total of 60 nurses were discovered.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The random sampling technique, which is a method of drawing a portion (or sample) of a population from the total population, was used.

Random sampling technique was used to select the subjects that supplied information relevant to the study. All the hospitals were used but to select the respondents in each hospital, numbers was assigned to each name found in the registers. The assigned number was then written on pieces of paper, wrapped and arranged in a container. From the container, the pieces of paper with numbers were picked randomly until the numbers of subjects desired have been picked. The subjects that helped in responding to the questionnaire are the nursing mothers that visit the hospitals as well as the nurses that work in the hospitals within Oyo East local government area.

The researcher sampled a representative number of nursing mothers and nurses in the population. To speak for the population, a sample of one-third (1/3) or thirty three percent (33%) of the whole population was chosen. The number so picked made up the sample of 150 nursing mothers and 20 nurses in the area of study.

Research Instrument

Hornby (1991) defined instrument as the implement or apparatus used in performing an action. Instrument in research (often called assessment or evaluation instruments) also means tools employed in gathering information about specific aspects of human behaviours.

The instrument used in collecting the data for this study is the questionnaire. Davidoff (1987) explained that the questionnaire allows researchers to collect required information quickly and cheaply from a large number of people at the same time. A comprehensive questionnaire was constructed by the researcher. It is to elicit some responses on the prevalence and rate of nutritional deficiencies and some possible ways of preventing food deficiencies among children.

The questionnaire contained two sections (sections A and B). Section A of the questionnaire requested information on personal data of the respondents. The information include age, religion and marital status while section B consists of questions and suggestions for the nursing mothers. On the other hand, the questionnaire for the nurses included; age, sex, religion and marital status. Section B also featured questions and suggestions on the prevalence of nutritional deficiencies of children in Oyo East local government of Oyo town Oyo state and how to prevent nutritional deficiencies in the area of study. In the questionnaire, each respondent is expected to react to the statements requiring ratings from "Strongly Agree (SA)" to "Strongly Disagree (SD)".

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was developed by the researcher and scrutinized by her supervisor. The instrument was further validated by the Health Education experts in the Department of Physical and Health Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin who are knowledgeable in health education, test construction and the area of study (Nutritional Deficiencies). They looked at the questionnaire critically and their contributions were used to prepare the final draft.

Reliability

To ascertain the reliability of the instruments, the researcher pilot tested the instrument among ten (10) nursing mothers using test re-test method. The first sampling test was carried out and collected immediately and the same respondents were used for the re-test procedure after one week. The two results of the questionnaire were

later compared and correlation co-efficient of 0.65 was obtained. The level of correlation was considered acceptable for the study

Data Collection

In collecting the data, questionnaire forms were distributed to the respondents for the purpose of having face-to-face interaction with them in case the respondents have any problems on how to go about completing the questionnaire. The illiterates among them were asked the questions orally in Yoruba language while the researcher helped complete the forms.

Method of Data Analysis.

For the analysis of data, simple percentage, mean score and chi- square were used at 0.05 alpha level of significance to determine the acceptance or otherwise of the hypotheses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

HYPOTHESIS ONE: CHILDREN IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA DO SUFFER FROM THE MOST COMMON NUTRITIONAL DEFICIENCY DISEASES

Table 1: Contingency table on Common Nutritional Deficiencies Diseases Suffered by Children in Oyo East Local Government Area.

ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Calc. X ²	Df	Critical Value	Decision on Ho
MALNUTRITION								
1. There are cases of children that are malnourished in my area	21(13)	80(79)	28(30)	21(29.3)	97.32	6	12.59	Rejected
2. Infants in my area are highly malnourished than the school age children	10(13)	81(79)	32(30)	27(29.3)				
3. Children that experience early weaning are malnourished, than those that feed longer on breast milk	8(13)	72(79)	30(30)	40(29.3)				
Column Total	39	237	90	88				

P-<0.05

Since the calculated X² value of 97.32 is greater than the critical value of 12.59 with 6 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected . That is, the children in the area of study suffer from most common nutritional deficiency diseases.

The findings as shown in Table 1 revealed that children from Oyo town, Oyo state suffer from commonest nutritional deficiencies since the calculated X² value of 97.32 is greater than the critical value of 12.5 at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. This showed that the majority of the nursing mothers believe that children in the area of study suffer from commonest nutritional deficiencies, such as malnutrition, kwashiorkor, marasmus, Anaemia, ricket, scurvy and obesity. This agreed with the opinion of Viedma (1988) which stated that nutritional balance is something that builds up day by day right from the conception of an embryo. Indeed, it is at this point that problems of growth and development begin. A great number of new born babies of the developing countries die or fail to survive because of vicious spiral of recurrent infections.

HYPOTHESIS TWO:

CHILDREN IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OYO TOWN, OYO STATE DO NOT SIGNIFICANTLY SUFFER FROM KWASHIORKOR.

Table 2: Contingency table for Ho₂

ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Calc. X ²	Df	Critical Value	Decision on Ho
KWASHIORKOR								
1. Children in my area suffer from kwashiorkor due to mothers ignorance.	22(23)	77(69)	37(31.5)	14(26.5)	67.44	9	16.92	Rejected
2. Kwashiorkor claim lives of children in my area.	27(23)	72(69)	22(31.5)	29(26.5)				
3. There are cases of protein deficiency such as kwashiorkor in children brought to the hospital for treatment.	15(23)	55(69)	31(31.5)	49(26.5)				
4. More children were admitted in the hospital due to kwashiorkor.	28(23)	72(69)	36(31.5)	14(26.5)				
Column Total	92	276	126	106				

Since the X² value of 67.44 is greater than critical value of 16.92 with 9 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. That is, the children in the area of study suffer from kwashiorkor.

HYPOTHESIS THREE:

INFANT/CHILDREN IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OYO TOWN, OYO STATE DO NOT SIGNIFICANTLY SUFFER FROM MARASMUS

Table 3: Contingency table for Ho₃

ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Calc. X ²	Df	Critical Value	Decision on Ho
MARASMUS								
1. Children in my area suffer from marasmus	40(23.75)	76(70.75)	27(29.25)	7(26.25)	52.78	9	16.92	Rejected
2. Nursing mothers were ignorant of the composition of balance diet.	26(23.75)	70(70.75)	26(29.25)	28(26.25)				
3. Frequent cases of marasmus were admitted in the hospital.	10(23.75)	53(70.75)	32(29.25)	55(26.25)				
4. Children die as a result of marasmus.	19(23.75)	84(70.75)	32(29.25)	15(26.25)				
Column Total	95	283	117	105				

P < 0.05

Since the calc.X² value of 52.78 is greater than critical value of 16.92 with 9 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. That is, the children in the area of study suffer from marasmus.

Table 2 showed that children from Oyo town, Oyo state suffer from Kwashiorkor since the calculated X² of 67.44 is greater than the critical value of 16.92 at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. Majority of the nursing mothers (respondents) asserted that children suffer from kwashiorkor. This is in line with James *et al.*, (1991). In their opinion they stated that medical research in nutrition was carried out after the Second World War in Africa, India, the Caribbean and South America, where major efforts were made to understand kwashiorkor, marasmus and other diseases of childhood. This view also tallied with Alade (2001)'s opinion that protein deficiency in early childhood leads to kwashiorkor.

Table 3 revealed that children from Oyo town, Oyo state suffer from Marasmus since the calculated X², 52.78 is greater than the critical value of 16.92 at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. Majority of the nursing mothers confirmed that the children suffer from marasmus. This is in line with Habicht (1983) who was

of the opinion that deficiency of energy and protein leads to stunted growth and in severe cases, to clinical marasmus and millions of death yearly in children. Also, in line with Alade (2001) who, in his opinion, said that marasmus is most common during the early years of children's life and it's fast becoming a prevalent disease among poor people.

HYPOTHESIS FOUR:

ANAEMIA AMONG THE INFANT IS NOT SIGNIFICANTLY HIGHER THAN AMONG SCHOOL AGE CHILDREN IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF OYO TOWN, OYO STATE.

Table 4: Contingency table for Ho₄

ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Calc. X ²	Df	Critical Value	Decision on Ho
ANAEMIA								
1. More children die of anaemia than other nutritional problems	44(50.3)	84(66)	11(11)	11(22.7)	43.33	6	12.59	Rejected
2. More cases of children with anaemia are admitted in the hospital for treatment.	35(50.3)	64(66)	8(11)	43(22.7)				
3. longer duration of breast feeding is essential for growth among children in their early stage of life.	72(50.3)	50(66)	14(11)	14(22.7)				
Column Total	151	198	33	68				

P < 0.05

Since the calculated X² value of 43.33 is greater than the critical value of 12.59 with degree of freedom of 6 at 0.05 Level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. That is, the children in the area of study suffer from anaemia.

The findings (Table 4) showed that children from Oyo town, Oyo state suffer from Anaemia since the calculated X² value of 43.33 is greater than the critical value of 12 at 0.05 level of significance, then the Ho is rejected. It was asserted by the nursing mothers that children suffer from anaemia. This is in line with Alade (2001) who stated that anaemia of nutritional origin are preventable diseases which occur where there is deficiency in one or more of the essential nutrients required for the synthesis of haemoglobin and the production of erythrocytes, and that anaemia is common in young children all over the world, especially in many of the developing countries like Nigeria.

HYPOTHESIS FIVE:

CASES OF CHILDREN ON ADMISSION BECAUSE OF RICKET ARE NOT SIGNIFICANTLY HIGHER THAN THOSE ADMITTED WITH OTHER DISEASES IN OYO EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN OYO TOWN, OYO STATE.

Table 5: Contingency table for Ho₅

ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Calc. X ²	Df	Critical Value	Decision on Ho
RICKET								
15. There are mineral deficiencies such as ricket in our hospital for treatment	10(7.75)	9(16)	1(1.25)	0(0)	19.27	12	21.03	Accepted
16. Children in my area suffer from ricket.	7(7.75)	13(16)	0(1.25)	0(0)				
17. Early weaning of children leads to Ricket	0(7.75)	18(16)	2(1.25)	0(0)				
18. Illiterate mothers do not feed balance diet during pregnancy.	9(7.75)	10(16)	1(1.25)	0(0)				
Column Total	26	50	4	0				

P < 0.05

Since the calculated X^2 value of 19.27 is less than the critical value of 21.03 with 12 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance then, the H_0 is accepted. That is, the children in the area of study do not suffer from ricket.

The findings (Table 5) also revealed that children from Oyo town, Oyo state do not suffer from Ricket since the calculated X^2 value of 19.27 is less than the critical value of 21.03 at 0.05 level of significance then, the H_0 is accepted. In this, majority of the nurses confirmed that children in the area do not suffer from ricket. This is in line with Samuel *et. al.* (1985) that it is a disease of the skeleton as a result of lack of calcium retention in the skeleton, a condition which is due to Vitamin D deficiency (sunshine vitamin). In a tropical country like Nigeria, there should be no reason why anybody should suffer from this disease as everyone can obtain enough sunshine throughout the year.

SUMMARY

The purpose of this study was to determine the nutritional status of the Children in Oyo East local government area of Oyo state, and specifically, relevant literatures were reviewed to determine the commonest nutritional problems among the children in Oyo East local government area of Oyo state. The variables include malnutrition, kwashiorkor, marasmus, anaemia and ricket.

The result revealed that the main hypothesis generated to solve the problem of the study was stated Null; that is the children in Oyo East local government area of Oyo state do not significantly suffer from the commonest nutritional deficiency problems, such as malnutrition, kwashiorkor, marasmus, anaemia and ricket among many others.

A descriptive research design was used with the study population which consisted of twenty nurses and one hundred and fifty nursing mothers in the area of study and both were randomly selected. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire containing eighteen (18) items. These items elicited information on the nutritional status of the children in Oyo East local government area of Oyo state. Results were presented using simple percentage, mean score and chi square at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The results of the data revealed the nutritional status of the children in the area of study.

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Corresponding author

Omosebi, M.O.

Department of Food Science and Technology, Wesley University of Science and Technology, P.O. Box 507, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria

Email: success2406@yahoo.com